

Designing a Tank Prioritisation Index for Sri Lanka: A Geospatial Approach

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Summary

Water storage is crucial for water security in countries with monsoon driven climates. This will become increasingly important in the context of climate change. Sri Lanka has had a network of approximately 23,000 small tanks which date back to the third millennium BC, which create a buffer to mitigate the impact of floods in the monsoon season and of droughts in the non-monsoon period. However, 21 percent of these are currently non-functional or damaged. This study uses a combination of tank survey data and global satellite datasets to design and implement a prioritisation for tank rejuvenation.

KEYWORDS: climate change, Sri Lanka, water storage, water resources, infrastructure rehabilitation

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1. Background

Water storage is crucial for water security in countries with monsoon driven climates (Anand et al., 2019). This will be ever more important in the context of climate change where we see increased variability in rainfall (IPCC 2023). Village tanks in Sri Lanka, some of which date back to the third millennium BC (Annandale, 2019) are one of the oldest traditional water harvesting structures. They contribute to water security by augmenting supply to agricultural production in several parts of South and Southeast Asia. They create a buffer storage to mitigate the impact of floods in the monsoon months and of droughts in the non-monsoon period (Anand et al., 2019). They also have an important role in the livelihoods of agriculture dependent populations (Rodrigues et al., 2012). It is estimated that there may be up to 23,000 small tanks across Sri Lanka but 21 percent of these are currently non-functional or damaged. In order to decide which tanks to rejuvenate, we need to consider a combination of supply and demand factors. Though there have been some smaller case studies to identify tank rehabilitation criteria (Kalaiarasi and Arul 2022; Anand et al., 2019; Saktivadivel, 2006) there have been few (if any) efforts to do so systematically, using a combination of satellite and survey data.

1. Methods

This study attempts to take a wider lens across all tanks in the country (**Figure 1**) and identify a set of criteria to first assess tank demand from the agriculture dependent population, and then identify a means to decide which tanks to prioritise to rejuvenate. The questions that are addressed in this study are (1) How do we identify the tanks in Sri Lanka that are most in need of rejuvenation? (i.e. supply perspective)? (2) How do we identify where agricultural dependent populations are located in Sri Lanka (i.e. identify demand)? (3) How do we identify parts of Sri Lanka which are most in need of small tank rejuvenation from a demand perspective? and (4) Which tanks should we prioritise for rejuvenation in Sri Lanka, considering both supply and demand constraints, as well as those which may hold the highest potential for groundwater recharge?

In order to gain answers to the questions above, we first computed estimates of agriculture dependent population at a 1km grid resolution. This involved consideration of district level estimates of agriculture dependent population, the location of agricultural lands, and use of 1km World Pop population counts with urban settlements masked out. We then considered the covariance of rainfall at the 1km grid level and computed a demand side index on the basis of these two statistics.

For the demand characteristics we considered the levels of sedimentation in the tanks according to UNDP survey data as well as the risk of soil erosion from the GLoSEM database. Finally, for consideration of the utility of the tanks for groundwater recharge, we considered the underlying rock structure in different areas of Sri Lanka, and their relative pump yield capacity using data from the Water Supply and Drainage Board Well Database (Joseph et al., 2022). Each index component can be viewed individually or combined under supply, demand and recharge potential indices. The Python code for the index generation is available on GitHub at github.com/fdlopane/SL-Tanks.

Figure 1 Comparison of total number of water tanks and functional ones in different Sri Lanka districts

The Demand-side Tank Prioritisation Index (TPI_D) prioritises locations where tanks are serving the largest number of agriculture dependent populations and where rainfall variability is highest, and is formulated as follows:

$$TPI_{D_DSD} = P_{ag_norm} \cdot R_{cov_norm} \quad (1)$$

Where, TPI_{D_DSD} is the demand index at DSD level, P_{ag_norm} is the normalised agriculture-dependent population per DSD district and R_{cov_norm} is the normalised valued of the rainfall variability of the area.

To establish where tanks supply is currently most depleted, we can consider the condition of tanks we have data on the level of siltation, and soil erosion risk; the Supply-side Tank Prioritisation Index (TPI_S) is formulated as follows:

$$TPI_{S_DSD} = (S_{norm} + E_{norm})/TPI_{S_max} \quad (2)$$

Where, TPI_{S_DSD} is the supply index at DSD level, S_{norm} is the normalised siltation score, E_{norm} is the normalised soil erosion score, and TPI_{S_max} is the national maximum score (to result with values between 0 and 1). In order to combine supply and demand, we simply take the arithmetic mean of TPI_{D_DSD} and TPI_{S_DSD} (**Figure 4**).

2. Results

Figure 2 shows the distribution of the agricultural-dependent population in Sri Lanka, while **Figure 3** shows the Demand-side Tank Prioritisation Index (TPI_D) and the Supply-side Tank Prioritisation Index (TPI_S).

Figure 2 Agricultural-dependent population in Sri Lanka: a) 1km resolution; b) DSD level.

Figure 3 a) Demand-side Tank Prioritisation Index; b) Supply-side Tank Prioritisation Index.

Figure 4 Combined supply and demand index at the a) district level, and b) DSD level.

Areas where tanks would be prioritised if focusing on where there would be the greatest population demands would be in the southern part of the Kurunegala district, the western part of the Anuradhapura district, and in the eastern part of the Batticaloa district. On the other hand, areas where tanks would be prioritised if focusing on supply side constraints would be in the eastern part of the Matale district, close to Kandy, and in the southern part of the Kurunegala district.

If groundwater recharge potential were to be taken into account, tank prioritisation DSDs are largely in Kurunegala and Anuradhapura, but note that there are still questions to be investigated around whether these tanks would be effective for groundwater recharge when compared to recharge from rainfall.

3. Discussion

Our study provides significant insights into the rejuvenation of traditional village tanks in Sri Lanka, a key strategy to improving the country's water security as it grapples with the impacts of climate change and seasonal rainfall variability. These tanks – some dating back to the third millennium BC – are not merely for water storage but are also essential for flood management and agricultural livelihoods throughout the island nation, particularly in the dry zones.

This study primarily aims to establish a systematic approach for prioritising the rejuvenation and rehabilitation of tanks. As previously mentioned, approximately 21 percent of Sri Lanka's 23,000 water tanks are currently deemed non-functional or damaged. In the context of constrained financial resources, this systematic methodology may help direct projects or policy interventions towards maximising outcomes (i.e., demand-side needs and supply-side constraints) with minimal resources. While previous case studies have attempted to meet similar objectives, they were generally on a smaller scale and lacked the comprehensive sophistication of our approach.

The approach of combining satellite and survey data to assess tank conditions and prioritise rejuvenation efforts, allow for a detailed understanding of both the demand-side needs and supply-side constraints. The identification of priority areas based on these criteria in districts like Kurunegala,

Anuradhapura, and Batticaloa for demand-driven rejuvenation, and near Matale and Kandy for supply constraints, demonstrates the varied water tank challenges throughout Sri Lanka. An interesting perspective that this study introduces is the role of these water tanks in groundwater recharge. However, while this potential is recognised, the comparative advantage of these tanks against natural rainfall recharge and percolation remains an area for further examination.

Still, the study is not without limitations. The exclusion of the tank cascades presents a notable gap in understanding the cumulative impact of rejuvenating individual tanks within a broader cascade system. Additionally, it is important to note our assumption that agriculture-dependent populations will be located proximate to croplands. It may be the case that some peri-urban populations are also agriculture dependent to some extent. Nonetheless, the methodologies developed here are still many steps ahead of what is currently available. The variables in the supply and demand side indices can be substituted or augmented with other parameters to increase the indices' sophistication, and the method for measuring an agriculture dependent population at a finer resolution can be extrapolated to other countries around the world.

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Biographies

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